

Sustainable Development – The Role of Green Technologies

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Introduction

Technology is the application of scientific principles, skill, methodologies, and creative mind to develop techniques and solutions to tackle problems to make the human life more comfortable. It is as old as the human civilization or even older. When the prehistoric Homo sapiens did not have any formal scientific knowledge, they applied techniques and made innovations to alleviate the problems of their daily life. Development of technology passed through many phases and periods which became very rapid after the industrial revolution starting in the middle of the eighteenth century (Fig 1).

Fig 1. Phases of development of technologies since their very early period.

Large scale application of technology especially for the manufacture of diverse products involves consumption of natural resources and energy. Since the resources are limited, concerns over their depletion grew from the middle of the last century. Simultaneously, emissions and wastes resulting from consumption of natural resources created the grave problem of environmental pollution and degradation that have diverse manifestation such as deterioration of air and water quality as well as global warming and consequent climate change.

To alleviate the problems of inefficient consumption of natural resources and pollution generation came the concept of green technology. In fact, the word *green* has a broad spectrum connotation. A technology that is environmentally friendly in its production or supply chain or application and exploitation is *Green Technology*. The word *Green* has

broken all barriers to make excursion into diverse disciplines and spheres of knowledge and practice. The word is most popular to epitomize anything that is environmentally friendly; it stands for a passion for environment and biodiversity. Thus, we say Green Chemistry, Green Technology, Green Energy, Green Buildings and Construction Technology, Green IT, Green Computing, Green Economics and often allude to many other things, apparently amazing – such as Green History and Green Philosophy.

What is Green?

Now, what is the origin of the word *Green*? It originates from an old English word *Growan* means ‘to grow with the color of living plants’. Thus, living and natural are the senses that this word reflects. Traditionally it has been used to mean natural, fresh, young, and even gullible. But, with an extension it implies something which is truly environmentally friendly. Green is not a label or certification. It is a way of thinking; it is the manifestation of a passion. Green development encompasses green activities in all spheres of development. The word came up with a big connotation in 1960’s when an improved variety of wheat gave dramatic increase in yield in Mexico. Then came improved varieties of rice and wheat - all under the leadership of Dr Norman Borlaug that saved the world from a war over food. After an unprecedented success in the 1960’s and 1970’s, came the second Green Revolution in the 1980’s with many more high yielding crops together with GM crops coming under its fold, although the response to this success has not been monodisperse.

With exponential development in technology in the second half of the last century and the growth in world population because of enhanced life expectancy, four major concerns gripped the humankind – Food, Shelter, Health and Environment. The concern for environment is the latest major concern and during the last two decades the concern became intense as did the deterioration of the quality of the environment. The threats to the environment are multifarious. According to the Hindu philosophy, the universe is made up of five ingredients – the Panchabhutam – *Jshiti, Op, Tegah, Marut and Byom*. About fifty years ago, people were mainly concerned with water and air pollution – only two threats, those on *Op* and *Marut*. But it did not take much time to discover that indiscriminate human activities took its toll on the other ingredients also. Kshiti or land in many places was found to be contaminated. Even, Tejah or energy was not totally friendly or acceptable. Leaving aside nuclear radiation, other types of radiation have also been causes of concern, often creating disputes. By now, the threats to the environment have become more complex, the remedial measures more difficult, and we have to struggle on many fronts – industrial wastes, municipal wastes, and of late, the electrical and electronic wastes – the E-wastes.

Deterioration of the environment has undoubtedly been the results of unbalanced development and growth. It should have been accompanied by adequate measure to protect the environment and judicious consumption, undoing the damage to the environment already done and conservation of scarce natural resources. But the urge to do so appeared through the attempts to develop technologies or to modify the current technologies in a way that these do not become atrocious to the environment, atrocious to Mother Nature. This is the origin of the green thought, the origin of a broad spectrum of green technologies.

In the backdrop of the present time, green technology is more than twenty years old although it did exist in different forms even in the ancient time. Green technologies are based on innovations that should adapt to the local context. A very recent World Bank report entitled *Green Growth, Technology and Innovations* elaborates many aspects and practicalities and practicability of many aspects of green growth. It says that Green Technologies comprise a

vast range of fundamentally different technologies that support wealth conservation and creation simultaneously achieving more resource-efficient, clean and resilient growth. Although the market for green technology is relatively young, it has garnered a significant amount of investor interest due to increasing awareness about the impacts of climate change and the depletion of natural resources. Green technology opens a path towards sustainable growth that can reconcile technological progress with the production limits of our planet.

Major and Emerging Green Technologies

Green technology has diverse ramifications with particular emphasis on climate change and carbon emissions which are now considered among the most pressing global issues. The following are some of the ramifications.

Alternative Energy

In order to provide a viable alternative to fossil fuels, many alternative sources of energy are being explored that do not generate atmospheric carbon. Solar and wind power are now among the most affordable sources of energy, and solar panels are affordable in many countries at a consumer scale. Solar roof tiles, an idea of the TESLA CEO, Elon Musk can greatly reduce household consumption of power from fossil fuels. Other alternatives, such as geothermal and tidal energy, have yet to be deployed at a large scale.

Electric Vehicles

About 16% of greenhouse gas emissions come from the transportation sector. Various kinds of electric vehicles including hybrid vehicles are now preferred because of various benefits including much higher energy efficiency. Many manufacturers are exploring ways to reduce automotive emissions, either by designing more fuel-efficient engines or shifting to electrical power. However, electric vehicles require a host of innovations in other spheres, such as high-capacity rechargeable batteries and charging infrastructure. In addition, the hard fact that many power grids still rely on fossil fuels limits the benefits of electric vehicles. This problem can be alleviated by harnessing alternative sources of energy, especially solar and wind energy as well as using green hydrogen, the cleanest fuel.

Sustainable Agriculture

Farming and livestock have a substantial environmental footprint, from the high costs of land and water usage to the ecological consequences of pesticides, fertilizers, and animal wastes. As a result, there are many opportunities for green technology in the area of agriculture. For example, organic farming techniques can reduce the damage due to soil exhaustion, innovations in cattle feed can reduce methane emissions, and meat substitutes can reduce the consumption of livestock dramatically reducing effective carbon footprint. Methods of vertical farming for growing crops with an amazing 95% less water and 75% less fertilizer have been claimed to have been achieved besides freeing up 80% of the world's agricultural land.

Recycling

Recycling seeks to conserve scarce resources by reusing materials or finding sustainable substitutes. While plastic, glass, paper, and metal waste are the most familiar forms of recycling, more sophisticated operations can be used to recover expensive raw materials from e-waste or automobile parts. Effective exploration of the concept of cradle to cradle in contrast to cradle to grave can make dramatic success in recycling.

Carbon Capture

Carbon capture refers to a group of experimental technologies that seek to remove and

sequester greenhouse gases, either at the point of combustion or from the atmosphere. This technology has been heavily promoted by the fossil fuel industry, although it has yet to deliver on those expectations. The largest carbon capture facility can absorb 4,000 tons of carbon dioxide per year, a minuscule amount compared to annual emissions. The captured CO₂ can either be sequestered in various ways or better can be utilized to produce fuels and chemicals. Model plants are in operation at a few places for production of green methanol and green fuels from captured CO₂. Hydrogen is the essential ingredient for this purpose and should be generated by water electrolysis utilizing solar power.

Green Architecture

Green architecture has the capability to cut down urban resource use dramatically, and making urban expansion sustainable. Green architecture allows for buildings to be constructed in a way, that they make use of natural light and ensure adequate insulation, so as to reduce energy consumption in cold countries. The construction materials can be derived from urban waste and other recyclable materials. This technology, in the near future, will allow for all buildings to be “passive”, not requiring significant additional emissions for construction and use.

Biomimicry and Artificial Photosynthesis

Regular natural processes are highly energy efficient and environment friendly. Biomimicry makes use of natural processes to generate diverse products with minimum consumption of resources and energy. A novel product is a self-healing material that has the capability to “heal” a wound from cut, torn or cracked.

Photosynthesis is the process by which plants take up carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and convert it to carbohydrates enzymatically by utilizing solar energy. As such, scientists are trying to develop a technology that will use sunlight, carbon dioxide and water to produce energy. Success at laboratory scale has been claimed by many. If this technology can be developed further, scaled up and commercialized, it will solve many problems at the same time - reduce carbon dioxide emissions and produce renewable fuel. A similar technology, yet to be commercialized, is cultivation of microbial cells for production of oils, the oil content claimed being about 70%.

R&D Needs

Researchers and policymakers have been attracted by the booming paradigm of green technologies and green growth. A few international journals are fully devoted to publishing and disseminating green research worldwide. Research efforts are admittedly broad spectrum. The scope of the topic is enormous. Only a few key areas are touched upon here.

Hydrogen is the condensed and absolutely clean energy of the future and will form the backbone of decarbonized economies. Renewable energy grid with integrated water electrolysis is the strategic technology for hydrogen production. The Proton Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyzer (PEMWE) that use noble metal catalysts and perfluorocarbon-based proton-exchange membrane is the most attractive. The early version of this membrane material was developed and commercialized by du Pont more than five decades ago and quickly captured the market of caustic-chlorine industries by replacing the classical mercury cell. The modern version of this material is now a versatile key component for electrolytic cell hydrogen production. However, developing countries, including India, do not have access to the technology and have to depend upon the developed countries. An alternative anion exchange membrane technology, cheaper and more efficient, is on the cards. A Korean

research team developed poly(flourenyl-co-aryl piperidinium, PFAP)-based anion exchange membrane that has displayed credible potential. Having a longer life, lesser cost and high performance are the key challenges. Comprehensive techno-economic and environmental life cycle assessments are required to evaluate potential hydrogen production clusters in favourable locations. However, green hydrogen is not yet cost competitive if compared to 'gray' or 'blue' hydrogen derived from fossil fuel sources. Besides electrolyzer technology, identification of the production system configuration is important to optimize the overall process. Three such configurations are shown in Fig 2. The pictures are self-explanatory. Parallel to development and refinement of technologies, environmental Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) costs need to be estimated to identify economic and environmental trade offs. Green hydrogen may lead to a series of derivatives such as green ammonia, green methanol, green fuels and a few others. In this context, PV technology, hydrogen storage technology as well as the technologies of these green derivatives deserves special attention.

Fig 2. Three system configurations for green hydrogen production proposed by Terlouw et al. [Energy & EnvSci, 15 (2022) 3583-3602].

Global warming and climate change have posed the toughest challenge and greatest threat to the survival of the human and the civilization. The blame squarely lies on unabated rise in carbon dioxide concentration in the atmosphere that has aggravated starting the middle of the last century. Conference of Parties (COP), the supreme decision making body under the auspices of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and a number of accords collectively drafted and signed by the great majority of the nations in the world appear to be a silver lining in the dark cloud of atmospheric carbon dioxide rise. Global temperature rise till 2020 is shown in Fig 3. The landmark Paris Accord (COP-21) converged on capping the temperature rise to within 1.5°C although the strategies and progress have been disputable. COP-27 which is now in progress will expectedly add some positivity to this essential exercise.

Fig 3. Global temperature rise from 1700 to 2020.

Perhaps the best strategy of carbon fixation is to adopt natural fixation by increasing the forest cover but the success may not be tremendous considering the burgeoning global population and the pressure on forest resources especially in developing countries that share the larger part of global population. However, two strategies have emerged as the alternative – Carbon Capture and Sequestration (CCS) and Carbon Capture and Utilization (CCU) - that need technological interventions. New terminologies are coming up though the basic objective remains the same. Some people prefer to call it Carbon Reuse Economy, but the terminology matters little, if any at all. CCS is an older concept and CCU is relatively recent. The former relies on underground storage in saline aquifers or in appropriate geological locations and on use of highly compressed carbon dioxide for enhanced oil recovery (EOR). Abandoned oil fields are also good locations for storing the greenhouse gas. But the associated cost of capture of carbon dioxide, compression to supercritical state, transportation to the selected location and pumping to the underground locations is too prohibitive. This is why CCS has not come up in a big way as a rescue.

The emerging concept that is considered to have tremendous potential particularly in years to come is Carbon Capture and Utilization, CCU. Chemical conversion of CO₂ for production of a host of chemicals and fuels has been contemplated as a green route of abatement options. This is christened as 'recycling' of carbon dioxide implying thereby that whatever quantity of the greenhouse gas is emitted from a variety of human activities may be chemically transformed back to materials that can be used as fuels, in particular. Admittedly, the idea has been debatable since the conversion is not as simple as it is advised. It will be absolutely necessary to go through thermal catalytic route for conversion of the molecule, a process which itself is capital and energy intensive. More importantly, it will inevitably need hydrogen gas as the co-reactant and will be required in huge quantities if recycling of carbon dioxide is contemplated at a meaningfully large scale. Carbon dioxide may be a 'feedstock' for a pretty good number of products. The realistic target products are mostly C1 compounds –methanol, formaldehyde, formic acid and methane. The techno-commercial questions that must be given preference for practical purposes are: (i) under what conditions, economic and technological, this strategy will be commercially viable, and (ii) what is the real potential of tonnage reduction of emission compared to the current generation and use.

The demonstration methanol plant of Carbon Recycling International (CRI) in Iceland and the pilot plants of Mitsui Chemicals Inc. for the production of formic acid from the same feed stocks are encouraging examples of CCU. Academic and industrial research work are in progress to develop better catalysts that will work wonderfully at mild reaction conditions

with accelerated reaction rates. Patents have been admitted to BP, BASF and pilot scale units have been built and run by companies like Haldor Topsoe, Lurgi, Air Liquide, especially to check the activity and performance of the catalysts they prepared and are trying to improve for better performance. Besides, a number of process simulation studies using laboratory kinetic data have been reported in the research literature. Alternative routes such as electrochemical, photochemical, photo-catalytic and enzymatic processes (the last one essentially attempts to mimic natural photosynthesis) have attracted a lot of research efforts, but these novel technologies may take a much longer time to spin off. Simultaneously, the potential use of green methanol is being explored. Foremost are road and marine transport and not-too-large quantity for in situ power generation by fuel cells. Techno economic feasibility and its sensitivity analysis have also been analyzed by some researchers with the conclusion that prices for electricity (for water electrolysis for hydrogen generation) and the product methanol price are the determinants. However, serious attempts should be made to generate electrolytic hydrogen through the green route of making use of solar or wind energy. Recent market price of green methanol is about three times the methanol from fossil fuel sources.

According to the UN interagency report published last year, sustainable transport—with its objectives of universal access, enhanced safety, reduced environmental and climate impact, improved resilience, and greater efficiency—is central to sustainable development. Sustainable transport system will provide services and infrastructure for the mobility of people and goods besides fast-tracking progress towards other crucial SDG's such as eradicating poverty in all its dimensions, reducing inequality, empowering women, and combatting climate change. As such, it is vital for achieving the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, and the Paris Climate Change Agreement at COP-21. Such goals can be realized only if the inter linkages between sustainable transport and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their targets are well understood and intentionally leveraged to resolve trade-offs and to benefit from potential synergies.

It is absolutely necessary to deploy new technologies to achieve sustainable transport at the desired scale and speed. Eco-friendly fuels and engines, autonomous vehicles, and intelligent transport systems (ITS) are essential for transport innovation landscape. However, large innovation gaps between countries, and between urban and rural areas exist that may perhaps widen unless adequate efforts are made to identify and close the gaps. A few technology solutions for the decarbonization of light-duty motor vehicles have been in the field that include ultra-high efficiency internal combustion engines, biofuels, hydrogen, and electric. For the realization of carbon reduction in full scale, it is necessary to find out ways of production of the above inputs to the vehicles following green strategies and routes. Further, the lifecycle environmental and health impacts of battery production and disposal for a billion electric vehicles in course of time remain a matter of concern. Safety concerns and a lack of infrastructure have been the stumbling blocks in adoption of hydrogen as a transport fuel. Ultimately, a global technology mix may emerge, although clearly EVs have a far greater role at present. Global sales of EVs grew from 1.3 million in 2015 to 5.1 million in 2018, achieving a 2–3% share of all new car sales.

The Indian Scenario

It will be interesting to have a close look at the progress achieved in our country in respect of green technologies and sustainable development in some form or other. The concept of sustainable development was enunciated in the Brundtland report in 1987 that urges the mankind to live within their means and not to exhaust everything leaving only little for the future generations. The limited natural resources do not allow us to be extravagant, we

should aim to development that is not short-lived, that lasts. The seventeen sustainable development goals of United Nations Development Program (UNDP) targeted to be achieved by 2030 include a few that can be achieved only by development and application of suitable green technologies. Four of these are more relevant in the present context - Affordable and Clean Energy (Goal 7), Industrial Innovation and Infrastructure (Goal 9), Responsible Consumption and Production (Goal 12), and Climate Action (Goal 13). India belongs to a few top countries in agricultural produces and had achieved food security. But per hector production of all agricultural items is well below the best in the world. There is enormous potential to apply green technology in Indian agriculture. We are very vulnerable in the energy sector with a huge oil import bill. Many of the households are yet to get the benefit of power supply. The problem may be partly solved by an effective and aggressive exploitation of alternative sources. India's current installed capacity of renewable energy is about 165 GW including large hydropower. The components of wind energy is about 41 GW, that of solar about 60 GW. The capacity is rising fast. In fact, India is at the forefront in planning harnessing solar energy as a frontrunner of International Solar Alliance.

Green building movement is getting shape by quite a few initiatives taken by the Confederation of Indian Industry (CII). Waste utilization and recycling and reuse have been much talked about but rarely practiced on a comprehensive scale. The unorganized sectors share a sizable responsibility but in an extremely inefficient and often hazardous way. Newer and sophisticated wastes such as E-wastes are being generated at an accelerated rate without adequate futuristic planning of taking up the challenge. Efficient water utilization in all sectors is another very important issue and needs monitoring and perhaps should be brought under certain regulatory framework. Above all, an urge for innovation, looking for and testing alternative ways and the courage of taking calculated and emboldened risk should be the guiding principles. Lots of opportunities are around that need to be welcomed with an open mind. The corporate sector has a great responsibility in all the above areas and many more areas that have not been cited in this article. The urge should come from within.

With an eye on exploitation of relatively clean fuels, substantial emphasis has been placed on biofuels. The Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas (MoPNG) on June 15, 2022 has issued National Policy on Biofuels-2018 Amendment, 2022. This has come into force on June 15, 2022. The following has been amended namely: Clause 2.2 which states "Vision and Goals" has been amended namely: "The Goal of the Policy is to enable availability of biofuels in the market thereby increasing its blending percentage. Ministry of Petroleum & Natural Gas (MoP & NG) has notified that Oil Companies shall sell Ethanol Blended Petrol (EBP) with percentage of ethanol up to twenty per cent throughout the country from the 1st of April 2023. Blending of ethanol in Petrol will gradually be increased in the coming years. A target of 20% blending of ethanol in petrol is proposed by Ethanol Supply Year (ESY) 2025-26. An indicative target of 5% blending of biodiesel in diesel /direct sale of biodiesel is proposed by 2030. This goal is to be achieved by reinforcing ongoing ethanol/biodiesel supplies through increasing domestic production". Clause 3.2 which states "The scope of the Policy encompasses following categories of fuels as "Biofuels" has been amended namely: "bioethanol": ethanol produced from biomass such as sugar containing materials, like sugar cane, sugar beet, sweet sorghum etc.; starch containing materials such as corn, cassava, rotten potatoes, agro-food / pulp industry waste, algae etc.; and, cellulosic materials such as bagasse, wood waste, agricultural and forestry residues or other renewable resources like industrial waste, vegetable wastes, industrial waste off-gases or any mix combination of above feedstock." Clause 5.9.1 which states "Ethanol Blended Petrol Programme" has been amended namely: "The total alcohol/ethanol production capacity in the country is estimated

to be around 700 crore litres per annum.” To implement E20 blended ethanol (20% ethanol in petrol), Second Generation (2G) bioethanol plants installed by Numaligarh Refinery in Assam and by Indian oil Corporation in Panipat are expected to go onstream this year. The former will utilize 5 lakh tonnes of bamboo (a forest product of the Northeast) and the latter will utilize 2 lakh tonnes of rice straw. Rice and wheat straw-based 2G bioethanol plants in larger number and higher capacity may be effective in solving the critical air pollution problem in Delhi, especially in the winter, mainly caused by unabated stubble burning. India produces about 500 million tonnes of agricultural wastes about half of which is burnt or wasted that can be a huge source of bioethanol. Hindustan Petroleum, Bharat Petroleum, and KRIBHCO also have taken up agricultural waste-based 2G bioethanol projects to have enough alcohol to be blended to supply 2E petrol.

It is interesting to recall the ‘nano-urea’ product of Indian Farmers’ Fertilizer Co Ltd (IIFCO) with a claim that a bottle of nano-urea is as effective as a bag of the urea fertilizer. While IIFCO claims to have conducted elaborate field tests of their novel products, a group of agricultural scientists have questioned the scientific basis of the claim. The debate will hopefully be resolved soon.

Another niche area of clean energy is electrolytic hydrogen. The National Hydrogen Mission of India was launched by the Prime Minister on the 75th Independence Day (15.08.2021) with an ambitious target of production of electrolytic hydrogen utilizing solar energy. A few highly resourceful entrepreneurs have come forward to produce green hydrogen, green ammonia and green methanol. Electric vehicles, including hybrid ones, have a large market in India and actions are on the way to satisfy the demand by indigenous production.

The future of mankind depends upon how effectively and sustainably the critical environmental problems created by the humans can be addressed. On the whole, green technologies hold the key to the success in this direction. Focused research efforts are necessary to have positive outcome not only in terms of research publications, but with equitable inventions and implementable technologies. We look forward for all positive outcomes for sustaining the human civilization.

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